

THE IMPORTANCE OF GAMING ACTIVITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN OF YOUNGER PRESCHOOL AGE

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By correctly educating, influencing three-year-old children, purposefully directing their actions, it is possible to achieve the formation of skills in them to independently develop the skills of eating, dressing, washing, assembling their place, and to thoroughly complete certain tasks and tasks. N.M.Shchelovanov, D.B.Elkonin and others believe that the child's achievements in growing up to the age of three significantly change his behavior, cognitive processes qualitatively. Nevertheless, the influence of adults on the growth of the child, the role remains in the lead, but the gradual increase ensures that it becomes more independent. But independence in preschool age is often manifested in the fact that within the framework of a child's personal opportunity, which is not so strong in practical activity, he acts without the help of an adult, although relatively little, in the sense of overcoming subordination.

The independence of a child is seen not only in his physical and mental capacity, in the realization of his own attitude towards a process that reaches his strength, without the support of an adult, but also in the solution of life problems that his strength, unable to master certain practical skills.

When reflecting on the psychological characteristics of children until preschool age, the satisfaction of desire, desire and intention that arises in it is carried out and guided by adults who decide to raise a child. The external and internal signs of certain difficulties in the upbringing process, manifested at this age period, are also repeatedly emphasized in psychological research and scientific and psychological literature, and first of all, stubbornness, negativism, stubbornness, whims are associated with such vices as the discrediting and devaluation of adults in the eyes of children. a number of scientific and psychological sources say that significant changes occur in the feelings and will of children of this age, and all this is clearly reflected in such situations as selfishness in a child, self-building, anti-social inclinations, attempts, stubbornness, jealousy.

N.Mascarina noted that the game does not arise on its own, for which there must be at least three conditions:

a) the fact that the child's mind contains a variety of impressions of the reality surrounding him;

b) the imagination of toys and educational means of influence of various manifestations;

c) the child's frequent handling and communication with adults. The style of direct influence of adults on the child plays a decisive role in this.

Children of preschool age gradually penetrate into the world of adult life and activity, and mental experiences leading to positive emotions, enthusiasm and boldness, which were previously manifested in collaborative activities, are transferred to the spiritual world of adults who have reached the level of an example. Now the child himself begins to independently find ways to enter the life and activities of an adult. He will later show the desire to participate in all aspects of the life and activities of older people and in interpersonal relationships. Therefore, it can be concluded that the role-playing game arises on the basis of a new relationship between an adult and a child. The role-playing game has a social

character in terms of its occurrence and is nothing more than a revival and repetition of the life and activities of an adult, and this game activity is also social in its content and essence. Role-playing game is considered a vivid example of the independent activity of a child, he gets acquainted with the life of an adult through the content of the game.

L.S.Slavina notes that in role-playing games, most often, the main attention is paid to moving with toys, in which the feature of Toy Movement acts as a leading activity for the subject, in the process the role becomes a secondary symptom, but the child performs some kind of task in games. The scientist writes that the conditions of role and play are not things that are no different for the child's movement, but the child approaches bodies as a reality that reflects his social content.

D.B.Elkonin noted that he recommends dividing preschool children into three groups according to the plot of specific role-playing games:

- 1) games on the plot of a household topic;
- 2) games that relate to the plot of production;
- 3) games with a socio-political plot.

By correctly organizing the process of educational influence on children, it is possible to plan the scale of the plots of the game. As strictly expressed in the science of children's psychology, when a child comes to kindergarten, his plot of the game reflects only events in the family marriage, as a result of taking walks, observing nature, the types of the game increase: a game such as a kindergarten, a zoo, a kitchen, a train, a steamer, a hairdresser, a seller is added. As the child grows older, the duration of the game also increases. A. P. Usova said that the game activity of children 3-4 years old is 10-15 minutes, the game activity of children 4-5 years old is 40-50 minutes, the game of older preschool children can be selected up to several hours. Even the plots of one type of game will last all day, plus even more. This circumstance cannot serve as any reason to say that the child, in the process of play activity, performs one or another aspect of life-

activity, an important aspect separately. Because the scientific data collected so far in Psychological Science cannot answer such problems.

D.B.Elko writes in his research that in addition to the plot of the role-playing game, there is also its content. In his opinion, the fact that in the game the child more accurately reflects the main aspect of adult activity constitutes the content of the game.

In addition to him D.B.Elkonin divides them into five groups based on the correlation of the content of the rules of the action game:

- 1) imitation of movement: imitative prostessual games;
- 2) games that dramatize a particular plot;
- 3) plot simple games;
- 4) games with a rule without a plot;
- 5) sports games consisting of exercises aimed at a specific goal.

The factor that prompted the child to play is his vision of the existence and interpersonal relationships of older people and his desire to test them in his personal activities, as well as his passion for direct communication with his peers, who are playing as a team.

Based on the analysis of the data collected in the science of child psychology, the following conclusion can be drawn on this age period:

- 1) in gaming activities, the child will be eager to demonstrate various actions to the fullest, to show the methods of their execution;
- 2) and later tries to reflect, summarizing all the actions.

Based on the above considerations, it can be said that objects that replace the life and activities of large people are the material support for expressing their movement in a generalized way. Therefore, the development of child movement in gaming activities is more dependent on the content of the game. Because the more compact and generalized the child's behavior is, the more he avoids reflecting the content of the adult's activities. Consequently, it goes on to practically fulfill people's attitudes towards things and each other and, therefore,

seeks to correctly express the social relationships of adults when acting with things. There is a chance that any game and the game will repeat its activity and interaction, its circulation in a specific way.

Accordingly, the game acquires social significance, allowing the child to learn valuable knowledge, practical skills, skills and habits created by mankind for centuries, which ultimately bring him to the very essence of interpersonal communication.

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